

Additional file 9: Overview of effect of weighting on main outcomes in final regression models (design effects/DEFF)

	<i>Specialist use</i>	<i>GP use</i>	<i>Specialist unmet needs</i>	<i>GP unmet needs</i>	<i>Emergency dept. use</i>	<i>Avoidable hospitalization</i>
<i>HV (ref. regular access)</i>	1.485	2.520	1.792	1.911	1.260	1.929
<i>EHC (ref. regular access)</i>	1.216	1.596	1.137	1.172	1.032	0.993
<i>EHC (ref. HV)</i>	1.257	1.746	1.174	1.259	1.038	1.229